

The Effectiveness of Employee Referral as a Recruitment Source

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Abstract: An employee referral scheme encourages a company's existing employees to select and recruit the suitable candidates from their social networks. As a reward, the employer typically pays the referring employee a referral bonus. Recruiting candidates using employee referral is widely acknowledged as being the most cost effective and efficient recruitment method to recruit candidates and as such, employers of all sizes, across all industries are trying to increase the volumes they recruit through this channel.

The present study has made a comparative assessment of various recruitment sources utilized by the organizations. The study attempts to evaluate the effectiveness of Employee Referral program in one of the esteemed organization dealing with IT and ITES. The data was analyzed using Correlation, Ratio analysis and Chi Square. Results indicated that the quality of applicants generated by E-referral is comparatively better or equivalent to other sources

Research concluded that Employee Referral as a recruitment source in the organization has highest conversion rate, offer rate, and offer acceptance rate.

Overall the research has provided evidence to support the need for organizations to develop recruitment strategy which incorporates a diverse range of sources to reach quality applicants in the desired target market. The organization should also improve the awareness and satisfaction level among the employees about the Employee Referral Program in order to gain maximum advantage from this source of recruitment.

Keywords: Recruitment; Employee Referral, Offer Acceptance rate, Conversion rate,

INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

Identifying and acquiring talent is one of the important functions in Human resource management. Employee Referral is the process of recruiting the candidates through reference given by the employee working in the same concern. Employee referral is an internal recruitment method employed by the organization to identify the potential candidates from the existing employees' social network

One of the underlying components of recruitment which traverses all three research areas and which is of key importance to the current study is the effect of the information about the job, the organization, or the recruitment process. Research on information effects assess whether the amount, type or presentation of information influences an applicant's decision to apply and accept a job, and whether these factors are related to post-hire variables such as the applicant's subsequent performance and satisfaction on the job (Barber, 1998; Breaugh et al., 2000). These measures have formed the basis of previous studies as the identification of clear relationships between such variables can assist organisations with developing recruitment strategies that will increase the likelihood that successful employees will be hired.

Information about the job and organisation is initially reflected through the recruitment sources organisations use to reach potential applicants. The impact of source information on applicant perceptions is of interest to the current study as this relationship is recognised as being a primary

determinant of source effectiveness. Traditional sources commonly used by companies include employee referrals, newspaper advertisements, employment agencies, and direct applications (also known as “walk-ins”). More recently organisations are introducing alternative sources such as internet recruitment to identify and reach candidates (Barber, 1998).

Source effectiveness, or superiority, has been the fundamental research issue investigated in relation to recruitment sources. This has primarily been assessed in terms of the effects of realistic information on applicants, the identification of demographic similarities between applicants and sources, and applicant perceptions of their fit with the job and organisation based on information provided by the source. Underlying these recruitment research theories is the concept of applicant self-selection, which implies that the recruitment source and the job and organisational information portrayed can influence the applicant job-choice decision process.

Generally, successful employee-referral programs offer some kind of monetary bonus for referrals who are hired and retained for a certain period of time (often 90 days). The reward amount should be sufficient to motivate employees to make referrals but not so large that they offer referrals who are unqualified for the positions. (David Hakkala).

Some companies limit the number of bonus-qualifying referrals that each employee can make per year. The purpose of this strategy is to encourage employees to reserve their scarce referral opportunities for the highest-qualified candidates that they know.

On the downside, such a policy can reduce the number of employee referrals per year.

A new employee's performance may not be measurable in only 90 days. In such cases, it may be prudent to offer a series of installment payments for referral bonuses.

Rather than pay cash bonuses, some companies offer their own goods or services to employees in exchange for referrals. This strategy is particularly suited to consumer-oriented businesses that sell items such as DVD players, car tires and other products that most workers commonly use.

Requests for employee referrals should be specific, including mandatory qualifications and qualifications that an above-average candidate should have. Most employment departments are awash with candidates, the majority of whom are under qualified. Employee referrals should add to the quality of the candidate pool.

To measure the effectiveness of an employee-referral program, it is important to track such metrics as the cost of employee referrals versus other recruitment channels, performance and retention of employee referrals, employee attitudes toward referral programs, and the percentage of new employees who are hired via referrals.

One benefit of an employee-referral program is that it can provide the employer with a source of passive candidates — those workers who are not actively seeking new jobs. Candidates referred by employees also tend to be of higher quality because the referring employee usually screens his or her referrals closely. After all, his or her reputation is somewhat on the line with every person he refers for a position. Referring a string of unqualified candidates reflects poorly on the referring employee's judgment, which may affect his or her career prospects. The usual monetary bonus paid to a referring employee for a successful referral can be a significant morale booster. It reinforces the tendency to refer high-quality candidates to one's own company, even when no positions are available.

Employee-referral programs can replace more expensive recruitment channels such as newspaper advertising, employment agencies, job fairs and so on.

Employee-referral programs are especially effective in the case of highly specialized positions that might be difficult to fill through conventional channels. People tend to associate with others in their professions, which gives them access to specialized or rare talent.

Overall, the benefits of employee-referral programs decisively outweigh the potential pitfalls. A well-designed and highly visible employee-referral program is a critical part of any company's recruitment strategy.

The primary focus of the current study is to assess the effectiveness of the Employee Referral as a recruitment source in one of the leading IT Organization in Chennai, India. Whilst the research on source effectiveness has examined a broad range of recruitment sources, to date there has been minimal exploration on the effectiveness of the Employee Referral in comparison to its rapid uptake as a recruitment source.

Job seekers learn about job openings through a wide array of sources such as advertising, websites, and job fairs. Although the effectiveness of these recruitment sources is one of the most intensely researched aspects of recruitment, the focus has been on post-hire instead of pre-hire outcomes (Barber, 1998). In addition, previous research has typically applied a very rudimentary classification of recruitment sources on the basis of the formal-informal distinction. Whereas formal sources such as job advertisements involve formal intermediaries that exist primarily for recruitment purposes, informal sources such as employee referrals do not rely on formal intermediaries to reach job seekers (Zottoli & Wanous, 2000). As such, for the past forty years, the main finding has been that employees recruited through informal sources show higher job satisfaction, better job performance, and lower turnover than employees recruited through formal sources (Breaugh, 2008).

Addressing calls for recruitment source research to be more theory-driven and to focus on organizational attraction (Breaugh, 2008; Zottoli & Wanous, 2000), Cable and Turban (2001) borrowed from the marketing literature to develop an innovative theoretical framework of the sources through which job seekers receive employment information. One of the most important premises of their model is that organizational attraction can be influenced by job and organizational information from a wide variety of sources, not restricted to the ones organizations intentionally incorporate in their recruitment activities. Their proposed taxonomy of recruitment sources consists of two major theoretical dimensions. First, the dependent-independent dimension refers to the degree of control the organization has over the source. Company-dependent sources such as

advertising are part of the organization's recruitment activities and can be directly managed to communicate the intended message to job seekers. On the contrary, company-independent sources such as word-of-mouth cannot be Recruitment Sources and Attraction directly controlled by the organization but can only be influenced indirectly through other recruitment activities. Second, the experiential-informational dimension represents the degree to which the source allows job seekers to acquire information through personal, vivid media (e.g., recruitment event) versus impersonal, pallid media (e.g., publicity).

Combining these two dimensions result in four distinct categories of recruitment sources. First, recruitment advertising represents a company-dependent informational source and consists of any paid form of non-personal presentation and promotion of an organization as an employer by the organization itself (Van Hoyer & Lievens, 2005). Examples include job advertisements, recruitment brochures, and recruitment websites. Second, as a company-dependent experiential source, recruitment events refer to events organized by the organization that allow job seekers to personally experience some aspect of the organization, for instance by meeting its representatives (Cable & Turban, 2001). Job fairs, open house events, and information sessions are examples of recruitment events. Third, publicity is a company-independent informational source and involves employment information disseminated through editorial media not paid for by the organization (Van Hoyer & Lievens, 2005). It typically consists of non-personal mass communication such as newspaper articles and TV news items. Finally, as a company-independent experiential source, word-of-mouth refers to interpersonal communication, independent of the organization's recruitment activities, about an organization as an employer or specific jobs (Van Hoyer & Lievens, 2009). Examples are talks with friends and advice from family.

Even though information from all these types of recruitment sources can affect organizational attraction, some are likely to be more influential

than others. In line with theoretical models of recruitment proposing credibility as an important explaining mechanism for the impact of recruitment activities on organizational attraction (Breaugh, 2008), the present study investigates how the characteristics of recruitment sources relate to credibility Recruitment Sources and Attraction perceptions which in turn might explain their different effects on organizational attraction. A source credibility perspective suggests that more credible sources of information are more persuasive in both changing attitudes and gaining behavioral compliance (Eisend, 2004; Hovland et al., 1953; Pornpitakpan, 2004). Perceived credibility consists of the perceived truthfulness, trustworthiness, and believability of the communicated information (Allen, Van Scotter, & Otondo, 2004). Applied to recruitment, this implies that recruitment sources vary in the degree to which job seekers perceive them as providing credible employment information, allowing to predict differential relationships of these sources with organizational attractiveness (Cable & Turban, 2001). Compared to company-dependent sources, company-independent sources are likely to be perceived as providing more credible information because they do not have the explicit purpose to promote the organization (Van Hove & Lievens, 2007a). In addition, job seekers tend to perceive information obtained through direct personal experience as more credible than indirect impersonal information, suggesting that experiential sources are more credible than informational sources (Allen et al., 2004).

Therefore, on the basis of Cable and Turban's (2001) taxonomy of recruitment sources and a source credibility perspective (Hovland et al., 1953; Pornpitakpan, 2004), it is expected that of all recruitment sources, job seekers will perceive employee referral as most credible given that it is a company-independent and experiential source. In turn, because of this credibility, it is expected to have the strongest impact on job seekers' attraction to organizations as employers.

Empirical support for these theoretical assumptions is scarce, given that only a few

previous studies have examined employee referral as a recruitment source.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The organizations' aim is to hire quality candidates and to reduce the cost involved in recruitment by improving the effectiveness of the Recruitment Sources. Since Employee Referral Program is considered as one of the most cost effective and efficient source of recruitment, there is a need to concentrate on it in order to gain maximum advantage from this source. The primary focus of research is to determine the effectiveness of employee referral program at the selected organization in Chennai, India. The research also aimed to find out the effectiveness of the employee referral program compared to other recruitment sources and check the awareness and satisfaction level of the employee referral program among the employees.

The population for the study included 300 employees from the organization and the database that was created by the organization over the training period during the recruitment drives. The sampling technique adopted was convenience sampling. The sample size used for the study was 150. Both the primary and the secondary data are taken into account for the purpose of the study. Primary data was collected using well structured questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from the company records.

The following statistical tools are used to analyze the data:

1. HR Ratios
2. Percentage analysis
3. Weighted average method
4. Content analysis
5. Chi –Square test
6. Correlation analysis
7. Frequency Analysis

HR RATIOS USED FOR THE ANALYSIS:

1. Yield ratio
2. Selection ratio

- 3. Offer rate
- 4. Offer-Acceptance ratio

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION
FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Table 1 No of Profiles generated from each source

Sources	Frequenc	Percentage
E-Recruitment	844	32.90
Employee	434	16.92
Placement	935	36.45
Direct Walk-Ins	352	13.72
Total	2565	100

Out of 2565 candidates who applied for interview, 36.45% are from placement vendors, 32.9% are from E-Recruitment T team, 16.92% are from Employee Referrals and 13.72% are from direct walk-ins.

Table .2 Frequency table for number of eligible profiles from each source

Sources	Frequency	Percentage (%)
E-Recruitment	808	33.86
Employee referrals	421	17.64
Placement Vendors	854	35.79
Direct Walk-Ins	303	12.69
Total	2386	100

Out of 2386 eligible profiles, 35.79% are from placement vendors, 33.86% are from E-Recruitment, 17.64% are from Employee referrals and 12.69% are from Direct Walk-Ins example, do not differentiate among departments of the same organization). This template was designed for two affiliations.

Table 3 Frequency table for source distribution of rejected candidates

Sources	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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E-Recruitment	593	33.8
Employee referrals	276	15.73
Placement Vendors	635	36.2
Direct Walk-Ins	250	14.25
Total	1754	100.0

Out of 1754 rejected candidates, 36.2% are from Placement vendors, 33.8% are from E-Recruitment, 15.73% are from Employee Referrals and 14.25% are from Direct Walk-Ins.

Selection Ratio: Consolidated analysis:

Table 4 Consolidated Analysis

Variable	E-Recruitment (%)	Employee Referral (%)	Placement vendor (%)	Direct walk-ins (%)
Number of profiles generated	32.90	16.92	36.45	13.72
Number of eligible profiles	33.86	17.64	35.79	12.69
Yield ratio	95.19	97.01	91.33	86.67
Tech selection ratio	43.56	57.00	47.07	32.34
MR selection ratio	78.12	79.16	77.11	70.64
HR selection ratio	78.18	76.31	70.64	70.66
Offer rate	26.6	33.41	25.64	17.49
Offer acceptance ratio	92.09	95.17	73.97	84.90

CHI-SQUARE TEST

CHI-SQUARE TEST BETWEEN SOURCE OF RECRUITMENT AND CANDIDATES FINAL STATUS

AIM: To test the significant association among the source of recruitment and candidate's final status

Ho: There is no significant association between the source of recruitment and candidate's final status

H1: There is significant association between the source of recruitment and candidate's final status

Calculation

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig.(2- sided)
PearsonChi-Square	36.450a	3	.000
Likelihood Ratio	37.233	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.503	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	2565		

Table 4 Table for association between the source of recruitment and candidate's final status

Result:

The significance level (0.000) is less than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted at 95% confidence level. Therefore there is significant association between the source of recruitment and candidate's final status

CHI-SQUARE TEST BETWEEN SOURCE OF RECRUITMENT AND CANDIDATES FINAL STATUS

AIM: To test the significant association between the source of recruitment and candidates offer acceptance status

Ho: There is no significant association between the source of recruitment and candidates offer acceptance status

H1: There is significant association between the source of recruitment and candidates offer acceptance status

Calculation

Chi-Square Tests

Table 5 Table for association between the source of recruitment and candidates offer acceptance status

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig.(2- sided)

PearsonChi-Square	92.610a	3	.000
Likelihood Ratio	102.837	3	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	51.692	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	2565		

Result

The table 5 shows that the significance level (0.000) is less than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted at 95% confidence level. Therefore there is significant association between the source of recruitment and candidate's offer acceptance status

Primary Data Analysis

FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Table 6 Awareness level among employees

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Highly Aware	22	14.7
Aware	60	40.0
Not aware	61	40.7
Highly not aware	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

14.7% of respondents are highly aware about the employee referral program. 40% of respondents are aware, 40.7% of respondents are not aware and 4.7% of respondents are highly not aware about the employee referral.

Table 7 Number of candidates referred by the employees

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
0-2	6	4.0
2-5	64	42.6
5-7	55	36.7
7 & above	25	16.7
Total	150	100.0

4% of respondents referred 0-2 candidates, 42.6% of respondents referred 2-5 candidates, 36.7% of respondents referred 5-7 candidates and 16.7% of respondents referred 7 & above number of candidates.

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	23	15.3
Agree	64	42.7
Disagree	56	37.3
Strongly disagree	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

115.3% of respondents strongly agree, 42.7% of respondents agree, 37.3% of respondents disagree and 4.7% of respondents strongly disagree about the awareness of navigation path in Ultimatix.

Table.8 Table for the respondents' knowledge in tracking the status of their buddy's profile

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	21	14.0
Agree	63	42.0
Disagree	59	39.3
Strongly disagree	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

14% of respondents strongly agree that they knew how to track the candidates' status. 42% of respondents agree, 39.3% of respondents disagree and 4.7% of respondents strongly disagree.

Table 9 Frequency table for the simplicity and user-friendliness

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	26	17.3
Agree	56	57.3
Disagree	61	40.7
Strongly	7	4.7

disagree		
Total	150	100.0

17.3% of respondents strongly agree, 37.3% of respondents agree, 40.7% of respondents disagree and 4.7% of respondents strongly disagree about the simplicity and user-friendliness

Table 9 Frequency table for regular updates about current job openings

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	20	13.3
Agree	65	43.3
Disagree	58	38.7
Strongly disagree	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

13.3% of respondents strongly agree that they receive regular updates about current job openings. 43.3% of respondents agree, 38.7% of respondents disagree and 4.7% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement.

Table 10 Frequency table for regular updates about candidates' status

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	21	14.0
Agree	67	44.6
Disagree	55	36.7
Strongly disagree	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

14% of respondents strongly agree that they receive regular updates about candidates' status. 44.6% of respondents agree, 36.7% of respondents disagree and 4.7% of respondents strongly disagree with the statement.

Table 11 Time taken for candidates to join the organization

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 month	35	23.3
2 month	102	68.0
3 month	13	8.7
4 & above	0	0
Total	150	100.0

23.3% of selected candidates join in 1 month, 68% of join in 2 months and 8.7% join in 3 months time and none above 4.

Table 12 Job satisfaction

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	28	18.6
satisfied	114	76.0
Dissatisfied	7	4.7
Highly dissatisfied	1	0.7
Total	150	100.0

18.6% of respondents were highly satisfied, 76% of respondents were satisfied, 4.7% of respondents were dissatisfied and 0.7% of respondents were highly dissatisfied with their job.

Table 13 Frequency table showing type of rewards provided

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Monetary reward	124	82.7
Non Monetary reward	26	17.3
Total	150	100.0

82.7% of respondents responded as Monetary rewards and 17.3% of respondents responded as Non-monetary rewards were provided for referring a candidate.

Table 14 Table for reward satisfaction among respondents

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	26	17.3
satisfied	57	38.0
Dissatisfied	59	39.3
Highly dissatisfied	8	5.3
Total	150	100.0

17.3% of respondents were highly satisfied, 38% of respondents were satisfied, 39.3% of respondents were dissatisfied and 5.3% of respondents were highly dissatisfied with the rewards provided for referring a candidate.

Table 15 Table for getting reward within stipulated time

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	14	9.3
Agree	46	30.7
Disagree	84	56.0
Strongly disagree	6	4.0
Total	150	100.0

9.3% of respondent strongly agree they get rewards within the stipulated time, 30.7% of respondents agree, 56% of respondents disagree and 4% of respondents strongly disagree.

Table 16 Frequency table for respondents' willingness to refer in future

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	124	82.7
No	26	17.3
Total	150	100.0

82.7% of respondents were willing to refer and 17.3% of respondents were not willing to refer candidates in future.

Table 17 Table for overall satisfaction with employee referral program

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	22	14.6
satisfied	61	40.7
Dissatisfied	61	40.7
Highly dissatisfied	6	4.0
Total	150	100.0

14.6% of respondents were highly satisfied, 40.7% of respondents were satisfied, 40.7% of respondents were dissatisfied and 4% of respondents were highly dissatisfied with the employee referral program.

WEIGHTED AVERAGE METHOD

AIM

To find the motivating factor to refer the candidate

Table 18

Weight age	Rank	No of responses				
		Referral bonus	Employee Benefits	Recognition	Job satisfaction	Others
10	1	128	11	7	4	0
9	2	22	98	18	12	0
8		0	41	62	47	0
7		0	0	63	87	0
6		0	0	0		150

Calculation

Weighted average for the factor Referral bonus

$$\text{Weighted average} = \frac{(128 \cdot 10) + (11 \cdot 9) + (7 \cdot 8) + (4 \cdot 7) + (0 \cdot 6)}{(10 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6)} = 36.57$$

Weighted average for the factor Employee benefits

$$\text{Weighted average} = \frac{(22 \cdot 10) + (98 \cdot 9) + (18 \cdot 8) + (12 \cdot 7) + (0 \cdot 6)}{(10 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6)} = 33.25$$

Weighted average for the factor Recognition

$$\text{Weighted average} = \frac{(0 \cdot 10) + (41 \cdot 9) + (62 \cdot 8) + (47 \cdot 7) + (0 \cdot 6)}{(10 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6)} = 31.05$$

Weighted average for the factor Job satisfaction

$$\text{Weighted average} = \frac{(0 \cdot 10) + (0 \cdot 9) + (63 \cdot 8) + (87 \cdot 7) + (0 \cdot 6)}{(10 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6)} = 27.82$$

Weighted average for other factors

$$\text{Weighted average} = \frac{(0 \cdot 10) + (0 \cdot 9) + (0 \cdot 8) + (0 \cdot 7) + (150 \cdot 6)}{(10 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 6)} = 22.5$$

Since the weighted average for Referral bonus is high (i.e., 34.47), it is clear that Referral bonus is the major motivating factor for the employees to refer a candidate.

CORRELATION

CORRELATION BETWEEN AWARENESS AND WILLINGNESS TO REFER

Aim

To find out the relationship between awareness of employee referral program among the employees and their willingness to refer in future.

Calculation

CORRELATION BETWEEN AWARENESS AND WILLINGNESS TO REFER
Correlations

Table 19 Relationship between awareness of employee referral program and employee willingness to refer in future

		Awareness	Willingness to refer in future
Awareness	P correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	1 150	.512(**) 150
Willingness to refer in future	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.512(*) .000 150	1 150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation value is 0.512; positive value of r indicates that there is a positive relationship between awareness of employee referral program and employee willingness to refer in future

CORRELATION BETWEEN AWARENESS OF EMPLOYEE REFERRAL PROGRAM AND NUMBER OF CANDIDATES REFERRED

Aim

To find out the relationship between awareness of employee referral program among the employees and the number of candidates referred by them.

Calculation

CORRELATION BETWEEN AWARENESS AND NUMBER OF CANDIDATES REFERRED
Correlations

Table 20 Relationship between awareness of employee referral program and number of candidates referred.

		Awareness	No of Candidate referred
Awareness	P correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	1 150	.947(**) 150
No of Candidate referred	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.947(**) .000 150	1 150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation value is 0.947; high positive value of r indicates there is a strong positive relationship between awareness of employee referral program and number of candidates referred by employees.

CORRELATION BETWEEN REWARD SATISFACTION AND WILLINGNESS TO REFER:

Aim

To find out the relationship between reward satisfaction and their willingness to refer candidates in future

Calculation

CORRELATION BETWEEN REWARD SATISFACTION AND WILLINGNESS TO REFER:

Correlations

Table 21 Relationship between reward satisfaction and employee willingness to refer in future

		Reward Satisfaction	Willingness to refer in future
Reward	P	1	.536(**)

Satisfaction	correlation		
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Willingness to refer in future	Pearson Correlation	.536(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation value is 0.526; positive value of r indicates there is a positive relationship between reward satisfaction and employee willingness to refer in future.

CORRELATION BETWEEN REWARD SATISFACTION AND NUMBER OF CANDIDATES REFERRED

Aim

To find out the relationship between reward satisfaction and number of candidates referred by employees calculation

CORRELATION BETWEEN REWARD SATISFACTION AND NUMBER OF CANDIDATES REFERRED

Correlations

Table 22 Relationship between reward satisfaction and employee willingness to refer in future

		No of Candidate referred	Reward Satisfaction
No of Candidate referred	P correlation	1	.923(**)
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150

Reward Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.923(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation value is 0.919; high positive value of r indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between reward satisfaction and number of candidates referred by employees.

CORRELATION BETWEEN EXPERIENCE OF RESPONDENTS AND NUMBER OF CANDIDATES REFERRED

Aim

To find out the relationship between the experience of respondents and the number of candidates referred by them calculation

CORRELATION BETWEEN EXPERIENCE AND NUMBER OF CANDIDATES REFERRED

Correlations

Table 23 Relationship between reward satisfaction and employee willingness to refer in future

		No of Candidate referred	Experience of the candidates
No of Candidate referred	P correlation	1	.434(**)
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Experience of the candidates	Pearson Correlation	.434(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation value is -0.434; negative value of r indicates there is negative relationship between experience of the respondents and number of candidates referred by employees.

CORRELATION BETWEEN REWARD SATISFACTION AND OVERALL SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEE REFERRAL PROGRAM

Aim

To find out the relationship between reward satisfaction and overall satisfaction of employee referral program calculation.

CORRELATION BETWEEN OVERALL SATISFACTION AND REWARD SATISFACTION

Correlations

Table 24 Relationship between reward satisfaction and employee willingness to refer in future

		Overall satisfact ion	Reward Satisfact ion
Overall satisfaction	P correlati on Sig.(2-tailed) N	1 150	.943(**) 150
Reward Satisfaction	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed) N	.943(**) .000 150	1 150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation value is 0.939; high positive value of r indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between reward satisfaction and overall satisfaction of employee referral program.

CONCLUSION

The research was undertaken to determine the effectiveness of the various Sources of Recruitment specifically concentrating on the Employee Referral program. The specific data

analysis in the sampled organization revealed that the Employee Referral is perceived as the best source of recruitment in the organization since it has the highest conversion rate, offer rate and offer acceptance rate.

It is also inferred that the number of candidates attending the interview from Employee Referral program is less as compared to all other sources In order to gain maximum advantage from the employee referral program,. It is necessary to improve the motivation, awareness and satisfaction level among the employees.

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